

Alleviating zinc deficiency in transplanted flooded rice grown in alkaline soils of Pakistan

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Zinc (Zn) deficiency, a widespread micronutrient disorder constraining rice production worldwide (Shorrocks 1992), is effectively controlled by field application of zinc sulfate ($ZnSO_4$) (Takkar and Walker 1993). A more convenient and economical method of alleviating the deficiency, however, is desired. In greenhouse and field experiments, we studied the comparative effectiveness of various management practices in alleviating Zn deficiency in transplanted flooded rice grown in the alkaline soils of Punjab Province, Pakistan.

The greenhouse study used surface soils (0–15 cm) of Miranpur (Aquic Ustochrepts) and Eminabad series (Typic Haplorthids) with pH 7.8–8.0, EC 1.0–2.1 $dS\ m^{-1}$, $CaCO_3$ equivalent 1.1–2.6%, organic matter 1.4–1.7%, and DTPA Zn 0.5–1.0 $mg\ kg^{-1}$. Pots containing 4.5-kg soil portions were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications (see table for treatments). Basal fertilization included 75 $mg\ N\ soil^{-1}$, 16.4 $mg\ P\ soil^{-1}$, and 23 $mg\ K\ kg\ soil^{-1}$. Dry matter yield, Zn concentration, and total Zn uptake were recorded after harvest (cv. IR6) of whole shoots at 50 d after transplanting (DAT).

All the management practices used increased rice biomass over that of the control (1.33 $g\ dry\ matter\ plant^{-1}$, $P < 0.05$), ranging from 25% (for foliar spray of 1% $ZnSO_4$ solution) to 79% (for Zn-enriched seedlings obtained by applying 5 $mg\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$ silica sand from a nursery bed) (see table). Various treatments, except for the Zn-enriched nursery, also enhanced the Zn concentration of whole shoots at 50 DAT from 16.2 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ (control plants) to 34.3 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ (foliar Zn spray). Weir and Cresswell (1994) have shown that most practices that increase plant tissue Zn concentration beyond the critical range of 15–18 $mg\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$ in whole shoots of IRR1

rice cultivars at the preflowering growth stage also increase plant growth. The substantial increase in Zn uptake of the treatments also showed that improved Zn nutrition enhanced yield (see table).

Subsequently, five field experiments were carried out using IR6 at Mangtanwala, Nankana District (Miranpur soil series [Aquic Ustochrepts]), Muridke, Sheikhpura District (Satghara series [Typic Haplorthids]), and Gujranwala (Gujranwala series [Udic Haplustalfs]). The soils were alkaline (pH, 7.8–8.4), calcareous ($CaCO_3$ equivalent, 1.0–4.1%), and nonsaline (EC, 1.0–3.9 $dS\ m^{-1}$), with 1.4–2.1% organic matter, 5.2–22.2 $mg\ Olsen\ P\ kg^{-1}$, and 0.5–0.9 $mg\ DTPA\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$. Experiments were laid out in an RCBD with four replications. Basal fertilization consisted of 100 $kg\ N\ ha^{-1}$ (urea) and 26.2 $kg\ P\ ha^{-1}$ (single superphosphate). The mean yield increase over that of the control (3.0 $t\ ha^{-1}$) ranged from 23% (for foliar $ZnSO_4$ spray) to 41% (nursery root dipping in 1% $ZnSO_4$ solution for 5 min) ($P < 0.05$; see figure). The yield increase in other treatments was

greater than the increase in the treatment using a conventional field broadcast of $ZnSO_4$ (27% over that of the control). The use of Zn-enriched rice seedlings obtained by applying 20 $kg\ Zn\ ha^{-1}$ to the nursery bed resulted in more yield increase (mean 31%) than with 10 $kg\ Zn\ ha^{-1}$ field-broadcast (see figure) in a variety of soils with variable native Zn status. Thus, contrary to previous findings (Takkar and Walker 1993), the use of Zn-enriched seedlings proved effective in correcting the deficiency even in severely Zn-deficient soils. In addition to seedling enrichment, high-Zn soil particles on the seedling roots may have contributed to Zn supply enhancement. Although nursery root dipping in 1% $ZnSO_4$ solution (41% increase) or in 1% ZnO slurry for 1 min (31% increase) also proved very effective, these practices are not adaptable at the farm level because of their high labor requirements. Nursery root dipping in ZnO slurry, despite being inexpensive (uses ~ 0.8 $kg\ Zn\ ha^{-1}$) and comparable in effectiveness to $ZnSO_4$ field application (Yoshida et al 1970), was not

Effect of Zn management practices on rice biomass production at 50 d after transplanting and on plant Zn content in a pot culture study^a.

Treatment	Dry matter yield ($g\ plant^{-1}$)	Zn concentration in whole shoots ($mg\ kg^{-1}$)	Zn uptake ($\mu g\ plant^{-1}$)
Control	1.3 a	16.2 a	21.6 a
Foliar spray of 1% $ZnSO_4$ solution	1.7 a	34.3 c	56.9 f
Periodic drainage of floodwater	2.1 ab	17.5 a	36.1 b
Nursery roots dipped in 1% ZnO slurry	2.1 ab	18.5 a	38.3 bc
5 $mg\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$ as $ZnSO_4$, mixed with whole soil volume	2.1 ab	23.5 b	49.4 d
Nursery roots dipped in 2.5% $ZnSO_4$ solution	2.1 ab	17.6 a	37.1 b
5 $mg\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$ as $ZnSO_4$, soil surface broadcast	2.2 ab	24.0 b	51.6 e
Zn-enriched seedlings, 5 $mg\ Zn\ kg^{-1}$, nursery bed	2.4 c	15.6 a	37.1 b
LSD (0.05)	0.6	3.4	1.9

^aValues followed by different letters are significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

Effect of management practices on rice yield and leaf Zn concentration (mean of 5 field experiments).

adopted as a routine practice because of its high labor requirement and erratic effectiveness (Takkar and Walker 1993). Similarly, drainage of flood water (resulting in a 20% yield increase; data not shown)

is hardly practicable at the desired growth stage because “flood-like situations” are not uncommon in the Punjab rice-growing areas due to heavy monsoon rains in July-August. Thus, considering effective-

ness, economics, and adaptability at the farm level, the only viable alternative to the ZnSO₄ application method is seedling enrichment or application of ZnSO₄ to nursery beds. This practice is also economical for managing Zn deficiency using a mat-type nursery in mechanical transplanters.

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Biochemical studies on rice seedlings under salt stress

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We estimated the amylase, peroxidase, and protease enzyme activity in four rice genotypes that have different degrees of salt tolerance. Pusa 2-21 and Saket 4 are salt-tolerant and Kamini and Sugandha are susceptible varieties. The enzymes were studied because salinity effects on seedling growth have been attributed to variation in activities of key hydrolytic enzymes such as L-amylase and protease (Dubey 1982, Kumar et al 1996). Similarly, peroxidase activity is related to the maintenance of cell membrane integrity through its involvement in detoxifying H₂O₂ to water (Levitt 1980), thus modifying the effect of free radicals under stress.

Seeds of four genotypes were germinated in control and salt solutions

(NaCl:CaCl₂:Na₂SO₄ in the ratio of 7:2:1; EC 12.0; and 16.0 dS m⁻¹) in sterilized germinating boxes lined with blotting papers and kept at 25 ± 2 °C in an incubator under controlled conditions with three replications. The embryonic axis of 7-d-old seedlings was observed to estimate enzyme activity using a standard procedure.

Amylase and peroxidase activities significantly decreased but protease activity increased under salt stress in all genotypes (see table). A decrease in activity of the hydrolyzing enzyme L-amylase caused by a decrease in water uptake has been reported by Dubey (1983). The decline in the free energy of water caused by the presence of salts in the medium limited amylase activity by reducing water uptake. In

contrast, protease activity increased under salinization in this study, confirming the findings of Reddy and Vora (1986) and Sheoran and Garg (1978). Salt-tolerant genotypes (Pusa 2-21 and Saket 4) showed a reduction of 18% and 20% at 12.0 dS m⁻¹ and 33% and 36% at 16.0 dS m⁻¹ for amylase, and 10% and 17% at 12.0 dS m⁻¹ and 15% and 16% at 16.0 dS m⁻¹ for peroxidase activity, respectively. In comparison, the decrease in activity of amylase (31% and 32% at 12.0 dS m⁻¹ and 46% and 48% at 16.0 dS m⁻¹) and peroxidase (15% and 15% at 12.0 dS m⁻¹ and 24% and 24% at 16.0 dS m⁻¹) in susceptible genotypes (Kamini and Sugandha, respectively), was relatively more. A decrease in the scavenging enzyme—peroxidase—under stress with rela-